

Intelligent analysis in cardiovascular disease using Decision tree in R Language

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ABSTRACT

As the most significant single cause of death on the planet, cardiovascular disease (CVD) in all its procedures is an essential and life or death problem. CVD is not an actual disease, it is affect the entire cardiovascular system. If analysis the common heart disease is blood vessels of the heart and brain. Overall, they affect people in future life in 30-44 age range. However, giving a cardiologist to a foremost 35-year-old, who will get a form of CVD already, has the disease's beginnings. These include coronary heart disease, angina; stroke; rheumatic heart disease; congenital heart disease; peripheral arterial disease, aortic aneurysm and dissection, deep vein thrombosis, and other, less common, cardiovascular diseases. Research and epidemiological studies have determined that 23.3 billion people died from CVD in 2018.

It has been predictable that by the year 2030, >23.3 million people will die annually from CVDs. Low and middle-income countries are more vulnerable to deaths due to CVD since they are more exposed to risk factors such as tobacco, less access to health care facilities, and lack of awareness. This paper predicts the patient's level. In cardiovascular disease with decision tree algorithm analysis of the NSP- fetal state class code (N=Normal; S=suspect; P=pathologic) in the R language with illustration form.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease, Decision Tree algorithm, R Language

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite credible improvements in the field of cardiovascular health raise added by scientific research over the past several decades, cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains to be the leading cause of premature deaths across the globe [1]. This topic is significant to analysis to for an estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, on behalf of 32% of all global deaths. Of these deaths, 85% were due to heart attack and stroke. Out of the 17 billion hasty deaths (under the age of 70) due to noncommunicable diseases in 2019, 38% were instigated by CVDs.[11]. To predicate the patient's level in cardiovascular disease using decision tree with r language.

Decision tree is a graph to denote choices and their outcomes in form of a tree. The nodes in the graph epitomize an event or special and the limits of the graph represent the decision rules or conditions. It is frequently used in Machine Learning and Data Mining applications using R.

2. CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

The cardiovascular is the coronary artery disease also known as skimming ischemic heart disease and it is where we have poor blood flow to the heart is supplied by the blood by vessels called the coronary arteries, but if we have a plaque as a result of atherosclerosis for example, [4] we have decreased blood flow to the heart tissues and if we get no blood no blood flow it

can lead to acute myocardial infarction and this is where we have necrosis of the Mario cardial tissue caused by lack of oxygenation and blood flow and as mentioned acute myocardial infarction is a result of an occluded coronary artery disease is associated with angina which occurs when there is a temporary loss of blood supply to the heart and this causes chest pain there are two types of angina stable angina and unstable angina, stable is where we have a stable plaque and chest pain comes about upon exertion. Research and epidemiological studies have concluded that 17.3 million people died from CVD in 2008. Of the entire death takes place due to CVD, 80% of the deaths are from low-middle income countries. It has been projected that by the year 2030, >23.3 million people will die annually from CVDs [5] Until, the late twenties, we were aware of the risks factors, such as smoking, hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes, fatness, inactive lifestyle, and dietary factors were responsible for the premature deaths due to CVD. To be more suitable, the risk factors are classified as modifiable and non-modifiable ones. The non-modifiable dangers are, age, sex, and familial history, and among the modifiable ones are hypertension, tobacco tradition, raised blood glucose, absence of physical movement, immoral rule and obesity. When the occurrence of cardiovascular disease was not explained completely on the basis of modifiable and non-modifiable ones, the examination of extra indicators and risks were conscripted which might answer and expose the relationship and could be of great help in risk stratification and improving treatment directed towards specific group or population. Main care amenities and indicate an increased risk of heart attack, stroke, heart failure, and other complications. [6]

3. DATA SETS

Table 1: CVD Attribute Information

Nmax	histogram peaks
Nzeros	histogram zeros
Mode	histogram mode
Mean	histogram mean
Median	histogram median
Variance	histogram variance
Tendency	histogram tendency

CLASS - FHR pattern class code (1 to 10) NSP - fetal state class code (N=normal; S=suspect; P=pathologic)

4. DECISION TREE

A decision tree is a diagram of the likely outcomes of a series of related varieties. Divide and conquer, split into subsets and they pure all YES or all NO, if YES: stop and if NOT: repeat the all the process, in which subset new data falls into. Used either to drive informal discussion or to map out an algorithm that predicts the best choice mathematically. In the decision tree have three different kinds of nodes: unintended nodes, decision nodes, and termination nodes.

A fortuitous node, represented by a circle, shows the probabilities of positive results. [2] A decision node, characterized by a square, shows a decision to be made, and an end node shows the ending outcome of a decision path. The cardiovascular disease analysis the decision tree play major role.

5. TRAINING DATA AND TESTING DATA

Training data. This type of data formulae up the machine learning algorithm. The input data feed the algorithm by the data scientist, to get the expected output. So the training data evaluates the data repeatedly to study more about the behavior of the data's, and then adjusts itself to serve its intended purpose. So in this paper training data play significant role.

Validation data. During training, validation data fills new data into the model that it hasn't evaluated before. Validation data affords the first test in contradiction of hidden data, allowing data scientists to evaluate, how well the model creates predictions based on the new data. Not all data scientists use validation data, but it can provide some helpful evidence to optimize hyper- parameters, which inspiration how the model evaluates data.

Test data. After training and validation data are built, testing data once over validates that it can create accurate predictions. If training and validation data comprise labels to monitor recital metrics of the model, the testing data should be unlabeled. Test data runs a final, real-world check of an unnoticed dataset to confirm that the ML algorithm was trained meritoriously.

In this paper analysis, two datasets have their place in creating and training ML models, it's easy to see some overlap between them. In the cardio, data sets analysis difference between training data vs. test data is clear: one trains a model, the other confirms it works correctly, but confusion can pop up between the functional similarities and differences of other types of datasets.

6. R and packages

R is a language and surroundings for statistical computing and graphics. It is a GNU project which is related to the S language and setting which was developed at Bell Laboratories by John Chambers and colleagues. Through S the R can be measured in different implementation, and wide variety of statistical analysis like, Classical statistical tests, clustering, classification, linear and nonlinear modeling, graphical techniques, and is highly extensible [9]. R is the lingua franca of Data Science that covers an enormous repository of packages.

These packages appeal to various fields that make use of R for their data drives. There are 10,000 packages in CRAN, making it an ocean of quintessential statistical tasks

To implement cardio disease to predict NSP, in this paper have been analyzed the R and R packages, would be played a hugely significant role to get visualize output and with accuracy result. In the methodology elaborated about r packages, i.e. party and rparty used to plot results in the visualize manner.

7. METHODOLOGY

To make this decision tree, taken 21 features and 2126 observations, to analyze cardio, to transfer the numeric features to character, in the r program, used \$NSPF, in this analysis, plunging data in the training and testing data[10]. To analyze, the decision tree in the r language, invoked the r package called party to classify the training data, in this training data taken feature are LB+AC+FM according to datasets, the weights are analyzed, and the output is below.

1) AC <- 0,00aSmt!2B; criterion - 1, statistic - 263,403 2) LB <= 136; criterion . 1, statistic - 131.511 3) FM 0.111898; criterion = 1, statistic = 35.729

- 4) * weights - 405 3) FM > 0.111898
- 5) * Heights = 11 2) LB * 136
- 6)' Heights - 314 1) AC > 0.000634028 7) AC <- 0.002Z09945; criterion - 1, statistic - 52.155
- 8) LB <- 136; criterion - 0.999, statistic - 17.292 9) FM <B 0.0121396; criterion • 1, statistic = 42.826
- 10) * Heights - 133 9) FM > 0.0121396
- 11) * Heights - 7 B)LB>136
- 12)' weights • 78 7) AC > 0.002209945 13) L8 <= 110; criterion - 1, statistic - 18.889
- 14) * weight5 - 18 13)LB>110
- 15) 18<=1+7; criterion = 0.965, statistic = 8.87?
- 16) FM <- 0.2354892; criterion - 0.986, statistic - 10.725
- 17) * Heights - 742 16) FM > 0.2354892
- 18) * Heights - 12 15)LB*147

Figure: 1 Decision tree classification

The tree is generally upside down. Root at the top and leaves are the bottom [8] the most important variable to the prediction model is basically at the top. Out of the three variables we have used AC is the most important variable in helping to classify the observations into 1, 2 & 3.

If $AC \leq 0.001$ it goes to the left side otherwise it goes on the right side. Similarly, LB is less than 136, it goes on the left side, and if it more than 136 its go on the right side. If you are at node 3 if FM is less than or equal to 0.11, then will reach terminal nodes. So there are the decision nodes where we can look at the probabilities. The probability that the response variable equals 1, which means the patient, is normal and the patient is more likely to be normal at this point. Sometimes we have to prone the tree make it smaller. Similarly, we interpreted to another side of branches. If $AC > 0.001$ then the patient will be in a pathologic situation.

Figure: 2 Probabilities analysis in R

The r is very rich in visualization, the below diagram is more compact to analyzed the cardio patient, this diagram gives a more easy way to understand the NSP. If AC is ≤ 0.001 then, it take to the left side and LB, $P < 0.001$ and more than 20, then the probabilities show to Node 3, in this gives, 1 is likely too high so the patient seems to be normal. Once the tree is built, then easily predicting new cardio patients.

Figure: 3 Compact analysis in the decision tree

Henceforth in this paper, taking the validation datasets, 408 (patients) observations, and 23 variables, to predict the decision tree model classification, whether each one of them belongs to which categories, i.e. class 1, 2, or 3., if we observe that 1st patient is normal, 64th patient suspected and so on. Using rpart package plot, if $AC \geq 839e-6$ yes and less then-No, in the node 1 training data sets gives a clear illustration that 934 Normal, 33 is suspected and 21 seems to be pathological. So the below diagram gives the actual accuracy result.

(ywl AC >= 839e-G rjjTI

? \

£3 -oπM

FM<0.2

FM< 0 0013

Figure: 4 NSP predict model for Cardio patient

Misclassification Errors:

Table 2: Misclassification Errors in CVD

	1	2	3
1	1222	70	112
2	126	156	32
3	0	0	0

In this table going to be depicted is there are 1222 patients which are actually normal so lmeans Normal and 2 means suspect and 3 means pathologic, the 1, 2, 3 indicate the reality, so this is the actual classification, this 1 2 3 indicate the prediction from the tree model. The 1222 is patients predicted them to be normal, 70 patients who were actually suspect so that is second category but the model predicted them to be normal, so this is the misclassification, these 70 patients should have been classified as 2, but the model show that they are normal so this is misclassifications similarly 112 patient who were actually pathologic, were predicted to be normal by this model, it is not optimized model we are just looking at a table an trying to understand what it is telling us the numbers in the diagonal they indicate correct classification, the numbers that are off diagonal that indicates miss classification. If we want to identify the miss classification error, simply take the total off off-diagonal elements and divide them by total number of observations, the output would be 0.197 misclassification errors.

8. CONCLUSION

Cardiovascular disease is dangerous in the human life, in the globe death rates are high. In this research article using decision tree in r language, analyzed prediction level. And depicted different types of output, and as well taken the misclassification errors also. In the future will be going to be analyze in the hybrid techniques, hybrid in the preprocessing data sets and Marko Chain technique and Deep Neural Network to be prediction for cardiovascular disease, so that we may take get more accuracy level.

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